

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INCREASING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND ACHIEVING ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE COUNTRY

Karimova Gulzira Ikromali qizi

Doctoral student of Fergana State University

Fergana, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article is about the importance of increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises in increasing the economic power of the country. Additionally, the aspects that should be paid attention to by enterprises for the development of the industrial sector were studied.

Keywords: economic potential, sustainable development, circular economy, economic growth, "greening".

The economic power of the country is closely related to the economic potential of the industrial enterprises operating in them. The industrial sector, which includes many fields, plays an important role in stimulating economic growth, increasing employment and ensuring technological progress in the country. Increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises has a wide-ranging effect on the development of innovations, the improvement of the condition of infrastructures in various fields, the increase of the country's economic indicators and the level of general well-being due to the increase in the amount of currency entering the country.

The industrial network is the basis of the economy of many developed countries, by which the necessary goods and services are produced on a global scale. However, the development of industrial enterprises should be achieved with the rational use of available resources.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were adopted by the international community at the UN Conference on Sustainable Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in June 2012. These goals are included in the agenda to be

implemented by all UN member states in 2015-2030. The essence of the 9th goal of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), called "Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure", is to build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation [1].

We know that industrial enterprises take a high share in the destruction of nature. Due to this, in the present period, industrial enterprises are widely emphasizing the integration of environmental protection issues in production processes. By investing in green technologies, renewable energy and sustainable supply chains, they can contribute to the long-term prosperity of the economy while minimizing their negative impact on the environment.

The importance of increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises in the sustainable development of the national economy is very high. Firstly, increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises has a positive effect on the overall stability of the national economy. Their expansion and modernization will increase the level of production and directly increase the productivity of the economy.

Secondly, an increase in the economic potential of industrial enterprises creates a multiplier effect, which indicates a proportional increase or decrease in final income as a result of an increase or decrease in capital. For example, as a result of a growth in the level of production in industry, the demand for workers in enterprises engaged in the transportation and sale of finished and semi-finished products may increase, which will cause a ripple effect on the entire economy.

Investments made by industrial enterprises in research and development not only increase their efficiency, but also lead to the development of new technologies that can be used in other sectors of the economy. These innovations can lead to higher quality products at lower cost, more efficient supply chains and the creation of entirely new industries. For example, advances in automation, artificial intelligence, and green technologies are driving global change. Countries that

prioritize innovation in industrial sectors will be competitive in international trade and will be able to achieve sustainable economic growth.

Also, the development of industrial enterprises leads to the creation of new jobs. As a result of the development and modernization of these enterprises, new types of work are introduced that require special skills and further stimulate education and professional development. As a result of the increase in employment, national income, consumer spending, and the demand for goods and services increase. In a country with a highly competent industrial sector, the unemployment rate is low, social tensions are avoided and general economic stability is achieved. Table 1 shows the trend of distribution of labor resources in our country by economic sectors by years.

Table 1

Distribution of total employment between the agriculture, industry, and service sectors [2]

Sectors	1991 year	2022 year	Absolute change
Agriculture	41.4	25.9	-15.5
Industry	21.0	24.2	+3.2
Service	37.6	49.9	+12.3

From the above table, we can understand that the majority of the population employed in agriculture has moved to the service sector. It's a good change, of course. But considering that the main part of economic benefits is produced in industrial enterprises, the +3.2 indicator is not enough to achieve high economic growth in our country. Additionally, for development to be sustainable, it is essential to use employment opportunities in an environmentally responsible manner. In this case, it is necessary to implement measures to reduce the amount of damage caused to nature, to support industrial enterprises producing "green" products, to improve the skills of employees for the use of new techniques and technologies.

Increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises by investing in resource-saving technologies has a positive effect on the efficient use of natural resources, which is the basis of sustainable development. Industrial enterprises that value the maximum rational use of resources, reduce waste and reduce energy consumption contribute to the sustainable use of natural resources and play a key role in the efforts to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations.

It is known that industrial sectors play a very important role in the country's export potential. By increasing the output of industrial enterprises, countries can expand the types of exported goods, diversify export markets, and reduce trade imbalances. The increase in the export of the products of these enterprises not only increases foreign exchange earnings, but also increases the country's influence and ability to influence international trade flows.

In addition, the development of industry stimulates the development of important infrastructures such as energy, transport networks and communication. These infrastructures are necessary for the efficient operation of industrial enterprises and help to update and expand the country's general infrastructure base with the development of industries. A developed infrastructure increases the efficiency of the economy by reducing transportation costs, increasing energy efficiency, and simplifying logistics and trade. This, in turn, ensures the entry of potential investors who need a reliable infrastructure to carry out business operations.

Also, increasing the capacity of enterprises helps to improve the standard of living of the population. Industrial development leads to higher wages, which increases household income and overall consumer spending. As a result of its prosperity, more jobs, adequate wages and improved social services are achieved, and many people are lifted out of poverty and inequality among the population is reduced. A wide variety of high-quality, affordable goods and services will be created, increasing the availability of products for local consumers and businesses.

In conclusion, there are aspects that need to be considered in the process of increasing the economic potential of industrial enterprises, one of which is the integration of "green" technologies and environmentally efficient practices into industrial production. Through "greening", industrial enterprises not only increase their economic power, but also increase their prestige in the international community.

It is also important to apply the principles of circular economy. Through this practice, it will be possible to use resources wisely, reduce waste and costs in the production process, and develop a system that continuously reuses, regenerates and recycles materials and resources without disposing of them after one use. This will create new economic opportunities in various sectors of the country and, along with economic growth, will also have a positive impact on environmental sustainability.

References:

- [1]. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/rio20>
- [2]. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/share-employment-agriculture-industry-services>